

Religion: A Tool to Ameliorate Ethnicity for National Integration

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Abstract

This paper focuses on Religion: a tool to ameliorate ethnicity for National Integration. Ethnicity has been one of the major threats to national unity, leading to division, suspicion, lack of mutual trust and true relationship among various ethnic groups in the country. This, however, form the bases of religion as an antidote to the above scenario. The paper argues that religion in its wisdom is an indispensable element in ameliorating or reducing ethnic rife to foster National unity by appealing to the conscience of various ethnic groups in Nigeria to see all human beings as the same under the same fatherhood of one God regardless of ethnic affiliations. The paper also contends that religion can reduce ethnic rife to intensify national integration by appealing to conscience of various ethnic groups in Nigeria not only to cultivate the virtues of love, peace and truth, but also to replicate these values in their work places. The study adopts structural conflict theory which looks at social problems, such as agitation for self- rule, resource control, social inequality, injustice, cultural detachment and the search for ethnic identity, etc. as factors that triggers ethnic rife in the country. Findings reveal that ethnic rife in Nigeria is due to marginalization and neglect. The paper recommends that leaders of various religions should conscientize their members on the danger inherent in ethnic rife as this will help to eschew ethnic sentiments which will in turn intensify national integration.

Keywords: Nigeria, Ethnic Group, Ethnicity, National Integration and Religion

Introduction

Ethnicity has been a major threat to national unity, thereby leading to division, suspicion, and lack of mutual trust among various ethnic groups in the country. Though, social problems relating to social inequality, poverty, marginalization, the struggle for political power, cultural detachment and the search for ethnic identity, etc. are some the causative factors that give rise to ethnic rife in Nigeria. Although, there are suggestions made as solutions to problems of ethnicity in Nigeria. Some of which include, patriotism which calls for every Nigeria to make national interest priority rather than ethnic groups interest, government policies- which require the government at all levels (federal, state and local) to put affective programmes and policies in place to discourage ethnicity as to promote civic values, inter-ethnic marriage – to encourage people from different ethnic groups to marry one another and youth education-which encouraged the youths for exchange of cultural values, traditions and practices of one ethnic groups to another ¹ Unfortunately, all these suggestions made to solve the problems of ethnicity turned into charade. This paper, reflects on religion as a tool to ameliorate ethnicity for National Integration.

Methodology and Theoretical Framework

Data for this study were collected mainly through secondary sources (published books, articles in learned journals, and internet materials) The study also adopted “structural conflict” theory. Whose major exponent include Karl Marx, Max Weber, Talcott, Parsons and Ralf Dahrendorf. The main argument of the structural conflict theory is that conflict is built into particular ways society is structured and organized. The theory looks at social problems, such as agitation for self- rule, social inequality, injustice, exploitation, etc. as causes of

conflicts. The theory further maintains that conflicts occur because of the exploitative and unjust nature of human societies and dominations of one class by another. This is typical of the Nigeria society.²

Conceptual Clarifications

Ethnic Group

This is a terminology used to describe a group of people who have a common language and cultural values, a people with shared genetic and cultural traits; that mark them distinct from other people due to these traits; a group of people who identify with each other on the basis of shared attributes that distinguish them from other ethnic group³. Furthermore, it denotes a community of people who believe that they possess a common identity based on issues of origin, kinship and perhaps share a common language⁴. This means that ethnic groups are social formation, which is distinguished by the communal character of their boundaries.

Ethnicity

It is the contextual discrimination by members of one group against others on the basis of differentiated systems of socio-cultural symbols⁵. With regards to types of ethnic groups, there are over 374, ethnic groups in Nigeria. Some of which include, Hausa, Yoruba, Igbo, Fulani, Kanuri, Ibibio, TV, Ijaw, etc. In Nigeria, ethnic groups are always identified by certain traits such language, culture, religion and traditions. Often, these traits are regarded as marker of ethnic identity.⁶ Following closely are the manifestations of ethnicity. In Nigeria, ethnicity is seen in politics. Here, the formation of three major political parties in the 1950s, such as Northern Peoples' Congress (NPC), with Ahmadu Bello Sardauna of Sokot as its leader to represent the interests of the North), National Council of Nigeria Citizens (NCNC) with Nnamdi Azikiwe as the leader to represent the interests of the Eastern Region), and the Action Group (AG), headed by Obafemi Awolowo to represent the interests of the West, etc. in national affairs are examples.⁷

In addition to this are the factors that gave rise to ethnicity. So many factors trigger ethnic rife in Nigeria. It occurs when a particular ethnic group continues to be the custodians of power at the center, controls the resources, enjoys more infrastructural development (good road network, education and hospital facilities, constant power supply), etc., more than other ethnic groups; have more ministerial appointments than other ethnic groups. Here, other ethnic groups that make up the federation will feel abandoned, neglected, marginalized and deprived and begin to agitate for self- rule and resource control.⁸ Here, it is this marginalization and neglect that gave rise to the emergence of militancy in the Niger Delta region. The people feel that they have been marginalized and thus suffered long years of neglect without been adequately taken care of by the Nigerian state, even the oil multinationals operating in the area despite the fact that the oil which is the economic mainstay of the nation is being sourced from the Niger Delta region. Here, militancy became the option after long years of dialogue to address the above scenario.⁹

Also, it is this same scenario that gave rise to agitation for self-rule by the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPO) since the early 60s under their foremost leader, Dim Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu the then former military governor of the eastern region. The failure to achieve this dream has been responsible for the Nigerian-Biafran Civil War of (1967- 1970). Today, the agitation is still ongoing under another powerful leader in the person of Nnamdi Kanu.¹⁰ Other ethnic militia include, Odua Peoples' Congress (OPC), to represent the interests of the Yoruba and Arewa Peoples' Congress (APC) to protect the interests of the North. All this however, leads to division, conflict, suspicion, lack of trust and true relationship among various ethnic groups in the country thereby affecting National Unity.¹¹

National Integration

National Integration is the awareness of a common identity amongst the citizens of a country, is the bond and togetherness between peoples regardless of their religion, culture and language; it is the feeling of oneness

and brotherhood. Of importance here is that though Nigerians may belong to different ethnic groups, speak of different languages with different cultures they are still one.¹²

Religion

Religion is a complex word and very hard to define satisfactorily. This explains why scholars have not agreed on any definition. In any case, the examination of some definitions proffered by scholars will enable us have a glimpse of what religion is all about. In Emile Durkheim's own view, religion is a unified system of beliefs practices relatives to sacred things, that is to say, to things set apart and forbidden, beliefs and practices which unite into a single moral community called a church all those who adhere to them.¹³ Tagbo Ugwu defined religion as the relationship between man and what he regards as sacred¹⁴. For Milton Yinger, religion is a system of beliefs and practices by means of which a group of people struggles with the ultimate problems of human life; it is the refusal to capitulate to death, to give up in the face of frustration, to allow hostility to tear apart one's human association.¹⁵ Williams James defined religion as the feelings, acts and experiences of individual men in their solitude; so far as they apprehend themselves to stand in relation to whatever they consider the divine¹⁶. For Alfred North Whitehead, religion is what an individual does with his solitariness.¹⁷ The most overriding interest in all these definitions as Joseph Omoregbe, has pointed out shows that through religion a link is established between God and man.¹⁸

Suggestions to Problems of Ethnicity

To solve the problems of ethnicity in Nigeria, several suggestions have been made to include patriotism which calls for every Nigeria to make national interest priority rather than ethnic groups interest, government policies- which require the government at all levels (federal, state and local) to put affective programmes and policies in place to discourage ethnicity as to promote civic values, inter-ethnic marriage – to encourage people from different ethnic groups to marry one another and youth education-which encouraged the youths for exchange of cultural values, traditions and practices of one ethnic groups to another.¹⁹ Unfortunately, these suggestions yield no results as ethnic rife continues to rise.

Religion as a Tool to ameliorate Ethnicity for National Integration

Religion sometimes causes large social and political crises in our society, yet it is only religion that can lead mankind to appreciate the purpose of life and value of man in society. It is not only the most immediate living force for interpretation of the world around us but also an antidote for national unity.²¹ Religion does this by appealing to the conscience of the different ethnic groups in the country to see all human beings as the same under the same fatherhood of one God. People with this consciousness of oneness will think for the welfare of one another regardless of ethnic affiliations. In addition, religion possesses values such as love, peace, justice, respect, honest, to mention but a few. Here, these values when cultivated by various ethnic groups will help to reduce ethnic bigotry in the country. Thus, when these values are replicated in our work places, schools, markets, etc. will help not only to reduce ethnic rife but also intensify national unity.

Conclusion

Ethnicity has been one of the major threats to national unity, leading to division, suspicion, lack of trust and true relationship among various ethnic groups in the country. Though, social problems relating to social inequality, poverty, marginalization, the struggle for political power, cultural detachment and the search for ethnic identity, etc. are some the causative factors that give rise to ethnic rife in Nigeria. This, however, form the bases of religion as a tool to ameliorate ethnic rife for national integration. Here, one assured way religion can reduce ethnicity to intensify national integration is by appealing to the conscience of various ethnic groups in Nigerian to see all human beings as the same under the same fatherhood of one God regardless of ethnic affiliations.

Recommendations

The paper recommends that religious leaders should sensitize their members on the danger inherent in ethnic rife. When this is done, it will help to eschew ethnic sentiments and this will in turn help to foster national unity. Since God is a unifying element in every religion and as such the creator and father of all, here, various ethnic groups irrespective of ethnic differences should see themselves as the same under the same fatherhood of one God.

Endnotes

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